

THE RULES OF GIVING A DAN FOR THE SPORT OF TAEKWONDO

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ABSTRACT

This article provides detailed information about the rules of giving a DAN for the sport of taekwondo. In addition, general information about the proper fastening of belts in the sport of Taekwondo is also given.

TAEKWONDO SPORTCHILARIGA DAN BERISH QONUN QOIDALARI

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada taekwondo sport turining DAN berish qoidalari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan bo'lib yoshlarni sportga jalb qilish va taekwondo sportturiga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini yanada ortirish aytib o'tilgan. Yana aytib o'tadigan bo'lsak Taekwondo sport turida belbog'larni to'g'ri bog'lash haqida ham umumiy ma'lumot berilgan.

Boshqa sharq jang san'atlaridagi kabi, taekvandoda ham jangchining kiyimi majburiy ravishda kimono va to'g'ri bog'langan belbog'ni o'z ichiga oladi. belbog' sportchining darajasi haqida juda ko'p narsani anglatadi - belbog' ranglarining butun gradatsiyasi mavjud, unga ko'ra talaba imtihon va musobaqalarda o'z mahoratini isbotlagan holda yangi, yuqori darajalarga ko'tariladi. Yangi boshlanuvchilar oq belbog', eng tajribali jangchilar esa qizil yoki qora belbog' taqishadi. Belbog'ning rangidan qat'i nazar, uni qanday qilib to'g'ri bog'lashni bilishingiz kerak - to'g'ri bog'langan belbog' allaqachon g'alabaning bir qismi deb ishoniladi.

Tog'ri bog'langan belbog' jangda bo'ladigan turli hil ko'ngilsizliklarni ham oldini oladi va sportchilarning sport darajasini belgilab beradi. Quyida belbog'ning to'g'ri bog'lashni 6 qadamda korishimiz mumkin. Har bir to'g'ri bog'langan belbog' jangchilarda o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchni belgilab beradi.

Oq (10 gip) dan qizil belbog'gacha (2 gip) attestasiya odatda har uch oyda bir marta o'tkaziladi. Qora belgili qizil belbog' egasi (1 gip) 1-danni olishdan oldin kamida olti oy mashq qilishi kerak. Har bir inson 3,5-4 yil ichida 1-dan qora belbog'ini olishi mumkin, bu qobiliyat, mashg'ulot chastotasi va sinov-imtihonga bog'liq.

Belbog' tizimi

- 10 kip — oq belbog'
- 9 kip — sariq chiziqli oq belbog'.
- 8 kip — sariq belbog'.
- 7 kip — yashil chiziqli sariq belbog'.
- 6 kip — yashil belbog'.
- 5 kip — ko'k chiziqli yashil belbog'.
- 4 kip — ko'k belbog'.
- 3 kip — qizil chiziqli ko'k belbog'.
- 2 kip — qizil belbog'.
- 1 kip — qora chiziqli qizil belbog'.
- 1 ta pum — o'smir bolalar qora belbog'ining butun uzunligi bo'ylab qizil va qora (18 yoshgacha),
- 1-dan — bitta oltin bezakli qora belbog'
- 2-dan — ikkita oltin bezakli qora belbog' va hokazo 9-dan.

Usta darajalari

- 1-3 Dan — instruktor yordamchisi
- 4-6 Dan — Xalqaro instruktor
- 7-8 Dan — Usta instruktor
- 9 Dan — Grandmaster

9-dan faxriy hisoblanadi, u Taekwondoni yuksaltirishdagi xizmatlari uchun beriladi. Bu yuksak darajaga Qozog'iston, Rossiya, AQSH, Indoneziya, Gonduras, Ispaniya, Xorvatiya va Pokiston prezidentlari hamda XOQ prezidentlari - Xuan Antonio Samaranch, Jak Rogge, Tomas Bax, shuningdek, BMT Bosh kotibi Pan Gi- Munlar erishgan.

Boshlang'ich darajadagilar oq belbog'dan (10-gip) boshlaydi, 9-gip, keyin 8-gip va 1-gipgacha davo

1-qadam

Uning uchlari bir xil uzunlikda bo'lishi uchun kamarni oling va oshqozonga mahkamlang. Ikkala uchini ham orqaga qaytaring va o'ng tomonga o'tadigan uchini orqangizga orqangizga chap tomonga qo'ying.

2-qadam

Kamarning bu uchini oldinga keltiring, uni qorin o'rtasiga yo'naltiring va kamar ostidan pastdan yuqoriga qarab chiqing. Oxiri beliga osilib turishi kerak. Shundan so'ng, ikkinchi uchini yuqori doira bo'ylab torting, oldinga olib boring va kamarning ikkala qatlami ostidan yuqoriga siljiting.

3-qadam

Ikkala uchini ham mahkamlang. Pastga osilgan kamarning uchi silliq va burilmagan bo'lishi kerak. Uchini yuqori qismidan bog'lab, kuchli tugunga ega bo'lguncha kamarning ikkala uchidan torting. Tugunga osilgan ikkala uchi ham teng uzunlikda bo'lishi kerak.

4-qadam

Kamarni bog'lashda, uning ikkala uchi nosimmetrik bo'lishini ta'minlash uchun uning o'rtasiga, oshqozon ustida joylashgan joyga e'tibor bering. Kimononi joyida saqlash uchun kamarni har doim ikki marta aylantiring va bog'lab turganingizda uchlarini to'g'rilang.

5-qadam

Kamarning tashqi uchi har doim belbog'ning ikkala burilishini old tomondan tortib oladi va keyin tepaga chiqadi. Taekwondo belbog'idagi to'g'ri tugun gorizont ravishda bog'langan.

6-qadam

Agar siz boshlang'ich talaba bo'lsangiz, belbog'ni bir burilishda 160-170 sm uzunlikdagi belbog'yordamida bog'lab ko'ring, kelajakda tajribangiz ortib, siz belbog'ni barcha navbatlar bo'yicha ikki burilishda bog'lashingiz mumkin bo'ladi.

Ushbu davr mobaynida o'rganuvchi bazaga oid texnikani o'zlashtiradi (dastlab, odatdagi zarbalmi, keyin esa sakrash holatida bajariluvchi zarbalmi o'rganish amalga oshiriladi) va Taekwondoda qabul qilingan marosimlarni o'zlashtiradi (formani to'g'ri kiyishni o'rganish, belbog'ni to'g'ri bog'lash, kattalar bilan salomlashish va hokazo). Qora belbog4 - bu birinchi Dan va undan yuqori Dan darajasi sohiblarining ushbu o'ringa munosibligini belgilab beradi.

«Dan» darajasini berish faqat Kukkiwon ixtiyoriga yuklatilgan. Birinchi darajali yoki undan yuqori Dan sohibi bo'lish uchun Kukkiwonda imtihon topshirishni xohlovchilar 4-Dan darajasidan kam bo'lmagan sport ustasi tomonidan taqdim etilgan tavsiyanomaga ega bo'lishlari, ya'ni bu sport ustasi «o 'z q o 'l ostidagi» talabgoming imtihonlarga tayyorligini tasdiqlashi, bu qarorga to'liq javobgarlikni o'z zimmasiga olishi talab qilinadi. Biroq Kukkiwonga ariza topshirishdan oldin, talabgorlar xohlagan Do'jang yoki klubda instruktor yoki mahalliy miqyosdagi attestatsiya komissiyasi oldida amaliy test sinovlaridan ijobiy o'tishi

talab qilinadi. Ushbu o'rinda 15 yoshdagi o'smir va bolalar uchun attestatsiyadan o'tishning o'zigaxos ayrim jihatlari haqida to'xtalib o'tish mumkin.

Garchi bolalar Taekwondo bilan shug'ullanish faoliyatlarini xohlagan yoshda boshlashlari mumkin bo'lsada, biroq ularga dastlabki attestatsiyadan o'tish uchun o'n yoshdan kichik bo'lmagan yoshda ruxsat beriladi. Tegishli tartibda belgilangan amaliy test sinovlaridan o'tganidan keyin ushbu yosh guruhlarida Dan yoki 1 dan 3-darajagacha Pum darajasi sohibligiga erishish bo'yicha hujjat beriladi.

15 yoshdan keyin ushbu Pum darajasi sohiblari (yana yangidan tegishli testlar yordamida tasdiqlanish orqali) voyaga yetganlar uchun belgilangan 1 Dan 3-darajasida Dan sohibligiga erishishlari mumkin, biroq bu vaqtda ushbu yosh guruhi doirasida Pum darajasiga ega bo'lgan sportchining belbog'i butunlay qora bo'lmasdan, balki qora-qizil rangda belgilanadi. 4-daraja Dan sohibligi faqat o'smirlar 18 yoshga to'lganidan keyin berilishi mumkin. Shuningdek, Taekwondoda sport mahorati bo'yicha har qanday Dan darajasi sohibligiga ega bo'lish uchun nafaqat tajriba talab qilinadi, balki ma'lum bir mashg'ulotlar davri stajiga ega bo'lish talab qilinib, bu qoida va tartiblar Kukkiwon qoidalarida belgilab qo'yilgan, masalan, 1-darajali Pum sohibligiga erishish uchun sportchi bir yildan kam bo'lmagan faoliyat stajiga ega bo'lishi kerak.

Mana shu faoliyat davomida sportchilarga qilichlardan ,nayzalardan va hokazolardan foydalanishmaydi. Taekwondoda qurollar bilan ishlash texnikasi mavjud emas. Xitoycha ushu sport turidan yoki turli xildagi qilichlar, nayzalar ,qurollardan foydalaniluvchi yaponcha kohudo sportidan farq qilib, Taekwondo odam tanasining imkoniyatlariga tayanib ish tutadi, ya'ni odam tanasining o'zi yetarlicha darajada shiddatli qurol hisoblanishi mumkin. Shu sababli, Taekwondoda foydalaniluvchi yagona vositalar sifatida protektorlar (himoya vositalari) qayd qilib o'tiladi.

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